

23 TrainingThings

for Writing Learning Objectives

You want to create learning material – and you don't know where to start? Create learning objectives!

Learning objectives guide decisions for scope, content, appropriate exercises and assessments. They also help align expectations BEFORE a lot of effort went into writing learning material. This guide and the examples on page 2 are all you need to get started.

Define your target group

1. **Define the overall topic** of the learning content you are about to create.
2. **Consider target learners** current skill levels and experience (e.g. beginners or experts?).
3. **List potential challenges**, e.g. due to learning environments (e.g. online) or a specific target group (e.g. language, accessibility).

Keep Learning Objectives Measurable

4. **Ensure objectives describe an observable behavior** that is "measurable".
5. **Do not use vague terms** like "understand," "learn," or "know".
6. **Use one action verb per learning objective** aligned with Bloom's Taxonomy (see page 2).
7. **Write from the learners' perspective:** Who should be able to do what (see page 2).
8. Use **established learning goals** for research data management where possible.

Structure Learning Objectives

9. **Create course-level objectives** (broad outcomes)
10. **Break them down into lesson/unit objectives**
11. **Build a logical hierarchical structure:** what is needed to achieve the unit / course objectives?
12. **Ensure progression of complexity considering the cognitive levels** (see page 2)

Extra Features (Advanced)

13. **Specify performance conditions** (e.g. „in a clinical setting“)
14. **Add time constraints** (e.g. „within 30 minutes“)
15. **Define success criteria** (e.g. „min 90% answers must be correct“)
16. **Include further context requirements** (e.g. „after the completion of this course“)

Implementation

17. **Align training formats and teaching** with learning objectives
18. **Create exercises and practice opportunities** that align with the action verbs of objectives
19. **Align assessments and quizzes** with learning objectives
20. **Present objectives to learners** in a form that focuses on what is in it for them

Regular Review

21. **Schedule periodic objective reviews**
22. **Gather stakeholder feedback regularly** and update based on feedback and assessment results (if applicable)
23. **Document revisions and improvements**

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The examples for action verbs below are sorted into **Blooms Taxonomy**: a hierarchical classification system that categorizes cognitive skills from lower-order thinking (remembering and understanding) to higher-order thinking (analyzing, evaluating, and creating), used to guide learning objective creation, curriculum design, instructional strategies, and assessment methods.

Here is an example for a clear, effective learning objective – compared with an unclear, ineffective learning objective.

Clear and effective learning objective:

Data Stewards are able to list the five main benefits of DMPs.

Unclear, ineffective learning objective:

Learners understand the benefits of DMPs.

